

CASE REPORT

Surgical extraction of a horizontally impacted maxillary canine: A case report

Jean Elizabeth Dalaguan^{ID}, Rea Heidi Abestano^{ID},
Keithly Mae Leguiz^{ID}, Krisdee Mendez^{ID}, John Alfritz Tilos^{ID}

ABSTRACT

In dentistry, the canine is recognized as the cornerstone of the mouth and plays a significant functional role. However, in some individuals, there is a failure of the canine teeth to erupt through the gingiva, causing discomfort thereafter. In this case, a 16-year-old female patient complained about the pain felt in her right maxillary incisors and expressed concerns about the adjacent lateral incisor displaying tooth mobility. Treating the impacted tooth was of utmost importance. The impacted canine was surgically removed to prevent future complications that may lead patients to undesirable situations. A trapezoidal flap was designed during the surgical procedure in accordance with the position of the impacted tooth to gain access. The canine was then resected into three parts using a surgical bur and removed. The flap was sutured shut after the incision. Then, a recall appointment was scheduled a week later to monitor the patient's wound healing. For the benefit of many, this study intends to provide awareness to never ignore the discrepancies observed in one's dentition. It is important to establish early detection, prompt intervention, and well-managed occurrence of impacted canines should be determined.

Keywords impacted tooth, cuspid, tooth extraction, surgical flaps

Corresponding author

Jean Elizabeth Dalaguan, Southwestern University
PHINMA, Urgello Street, Cebu City,
jeah.dalaguan.swu@phinmaed.com, (0926) 728 1789

1 | Introduction

After the mandibular third molar, the maxillary canine is the second most commonly impacted tooth.¹ When the eruption sequence of the permanent maxillary canine tends to lag behind other teeth in the dentition, the tooth is considered impacted. Clinical

examination and radiographs can both be used to diagnose maxillary canine impaction. Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) can also be utilized to identify the condition of the specific tooth in a high spatial resolution.² The etiology of displaced maxillary canines remains unknown yet hypothesized to be both influenced by multiple factors and genetically acquired in nature.³ According to Dalessandri et al., the most commonly used approaches for treating mandibular canine impactions

are surgical extraction and orthodontic traction.⁴ Yet, the most desirable clinical course is early detection and intervention of potential impaction.⁵

Trapezoidal flap provides excellent access and produces no tension in the tissues. It also allows reapproximating the flap to its original position which speeds up the healing process. This report aimed to present a case of impacted canine management while raising awareness to never ignore the discrepancies observed in one's dentition.

2 | Case presentation section

Figure 1. A pus-filled swollen bump on the gums located at the upper right central incisor.

2.1 Chief Complaint

A 16-year-old female patient presented to the clinic with the chief

complaint of pain in her upper right anterior quadrant. On her right central incisor, a gum boil was present. She was also concerned about the mobility of the adjacent tooth, which is the right lateral incisor.

2.2 Medical History

There were no significant medical findings in the patient's history. No known allergies, and no history of illness-related hospitalizations.

Figure 2. CBCT scan: (A) frontal view and (B) sagittal view

2.3 Dental History

The patient has reported having oral prophylaxis once and no prior history of tooth extraction, tooth restoration, or receiving any dental treatment.

2.4 Diagnosis

Upon intraoral examination, the presence of a gum boil was seen on the

upper right central incisor (Figure 1). Alongside, a mobility test on her lateral incisor was done and revealed a Grade 2 tooth mobility with more than 1mm movement in a horizontal direction. CBCT scan (Figure 2) was performed and exposed a Type A displaced maxillary canine. Vital signs and laboratory tests were taken to evaluate the patient's health prior to the extraction of the offending tooth. The results of the complete blood count and prothrombin time appeared to be normal, indicating that the patient was able to receive the treatment.

2.5 Prognosis

After a week, a recall visit was scheduled to check the patient's wound healing. The extraction of the upper right impacted canine has a good prognosis with no postoperative problems.

Figure 4. Open surgical technique with a trapezoidal flap. (A) Gaining access (B-C) Establishing trapezoidal flap (D) Successful removal of the impacted canine.

Figure 3. Suturing the flap

2.6 Treatment

With the patient's consent, she decided to undergo the tooth extraction of an impacted maxillary canine due to the excruciating discomfort she was experiencing. Orthodontic treatment was possibly not chosen since the case requires immediate intervention and may impose a much higher cost to the patient. If orthodontic traction is made, orthodontic consideration depends on the location of the impacted canine in the dental arch.

To reduce the incidence of postoperative complications, drugs were requested to take 1 hour before the surgery. These include 2 capsules of Amoxicillin 500mg as a prophylactic antibiotic, due to the presence of an abscess on tooth #11. Then, 1 capsule of Mefenamic acid 250mg, 1 capsule of Tranexamic acid 250mg, and 1 capsule of Dexamethasone 4mg. Lidocaine HCl 2% (Lignospan) with epinephrine 1:100,000 was the solution of choice to anesthetize the patient, through local infiltration technique. During the

procedure, it was noted that four carpules were consumed.

In gaining access, a trapezoidal flap was used where a vertical releasing incision was made from the interdental papilla in between tooth #21 and #22, and the other one between tooth #12 and #14 (Figure 3). When the offending tooth was accessed, it was carefully extracted where it was resected into three. After the successful removal of the impacted canine, the flap was sutured shut using chromic catgut, known as an absorbable material (Figure 4).

Figure 5. A week after the extraction. (A) Frontal view (B) Occlusal view

Postoperative medications were then prescribed, 20 capsules of Amoxicillin 500mg taken every 8 hrs. for 7 days, 9 capsules of Celebrex (Celecoxib) 200mg, 1 capsule taken every 12 hrs. for 5 days and so thus 11

capsules of Tranexamic acid 250mg taken every 8 hrs. for 4 days to control post-op bleeding.

This treatment procedure was conducted last August 10, 2022. After a week, the patient came back for post-op monitoring (Figure 5), and presented no post-op complications, which indicates a good prognosis. The patient was requested to visit again on the tenth day, but did not come back and just updated that the sutures had resorbed on their own.

3 | Discussion

This case report focuses on the surgical extraction of an impacted maxillary right canine on a 16-year-old female patient who experienced chronic intense pain on her maxillary right anteriors with concerns about the mobility of the adjacent lateral incisor. The most often afflicted teeth are the maxillary lateral incisors associated with root resorption, followed by the maxillary central incisor, confirmed by previous studies.^{6,7} Upon clinical examination, it was determined that a grade 2 tooth mobility was present on her tooth #12 and a gum boil was also evident on tooth #11.

There are various treatment options for impacted cuspids, such as autotransplantation of the tooth, surgical exposure of the canine and bringing it into the line of occlusion through orthodontic treatment, or surgical removal.⁸ But, as a result of the

delayed detection and intervention, it led the patient to an expensive and complex treatment via surgical removal of the impacted tooth.⁹ To gain access, a trapezoidal flap was used with two oblique vertical releasing incisions extending to the labial vestibule and a horizontal incision along the gingiva. Semilunar flaps are usually used, but for cases that are deeply impacted, trapezoid flaps (3 sided) may be used.¹⁰ Trapezoidal flaps are indicated when extensive surgical field is required especially when a two-sided flap is inadequate. Trapezoidal flaps are advantageous for its good accessibility and visualization with minimal tension on the tissue, and good reapproximation of tissue to the original position. Chromic catgut is an absorbable suture made from collagen derived from healthy sheep or cattle intestine tanned with Chromium salts to facilitate handling and resist tissue degradation. Its absorption is like that of plain Catgut but it takes longer time and with moderate tissue reaction.¹¹

This study aimed to address that a missed diagnosis of an impacted canine may pose a risk of damage to the roots of neighboring teeth, depending on the position of the impacted canine. In the worst-case scenario, this may lead to the extraction of the offending tooth, as well as extensive, prolonged, and even more expensive treatment.^{12,13}

4 | Conclusions

Regarding function and aesthetics, managing impacted canines is crucial. There are several surgical and orthodontic techniques that can be used to manage impacted maxillary canines. The kind and degree of the impaction, as well as how it affects the adjacent teeth, will determine the course of treatment. In this case, a horizontally impacted right maxillary canine (tooth #13) was surgically removed along with the gum boil in the maxillary right central incisor (tooth #11) due to the significant risk of damaging nearby tooth roots. It is preferable to have the impacted maxillary canine removed as soon as possible if it is in an unfavorable position and cannot be put into a normal occlusion to prevent future problems and complications.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, K.M.; original draft preparation, K.M., J.D, R.A.; Validation, K.M., J.D., J.T., R.A., K.L.; Data Curation, K.M., J.D., K.L., R.A., J.T.; Writing - Review & Editing, K.M., J.D., R.A., K.L., J.T.

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Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics

Committee of Southwestern University
PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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